

Are the major knowledge-producing countries converging in science and technology capabilities?¹

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Abstract

The global production of scientific and technology knowledge continues to grow. Advanced western countries such as the US and the EU countries continue to lead science and technology (S&T) in the world. The emergence of other knowledge-producing countries that occupy prominent positions in knowledge production have been changing the geography of world science and technology. By investigating the production of scientific publications and patents from a sample of traditional S&T powerhouses and the main emerging knowledge-producing countries, this paper attempts to test whether the remarkable development of S&T systems in the latter in the past few decades has led to a convergence with the former countries in S&T capabilities. The empirical analysis of convergence highlights the presence of clubs of convergence instead of absolute convergence. Four groups of countries have been identified as converging regarding their scientific publications per capita, and six convergence clubs have emerged when the production of patents per capita is considered.

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1. Introduction

In a globalized world, competition occurs not only among firms but also among innovation systems and economies (Loikkanen et al., 2009). Long-term competitiveness signals the innovative capability of economies (Lundvall, 2016). A country's science and technology (S&T) systems contribute to sharpen its innovative capabilities (Castellacci and Natera, 2015); strong S&T systems may reduce dependence on knowledge generated abroad and attract multinational corporations and foreign investors (Horta, 2018). The rapid growth in the creation and diffusion of knowledge in the past few decades has led to a world economy that has become very competitive (Tchamyu, 2017).

The leaders of the world economy, the United States and the European Union, developed their S&T systems earlier than other countries, and have retained a dominant position as S&T powerhouses worldwide since the middle of the last century; from the 1960s, Japan began catching up, reaching a position among the leaders (Adams, 2012; Radosevic and Yoruk, 2014; Kim and Lee, 2015; Horta, 2018). More recently, newly industrialized Asian countries (NICs) (Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore, and South Korea) 'have achieved remarkable levels of science and technology production' (Wong and Goh, 2012:56) in their transition toward post-industrialized knowledge-based economies (Wong and Goh, 2015). For instance, Hu (2015) points out that Japan and South Korea are close to or at the world technology frontier. In addition, from the beginning of the twenty-first century, the BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) 'are becoming one of the world centres of producers of new knowledge, modern technology, and innovative development' (Shashnov and Kotsemir, 2018:1116). As Crescenzi et al. (2012:1055) note in relation to innovation, BRICS countries 'are perhaps beginning to move closer to the Triad's leadership position'. Especially remarkable is the rapid growth of China's indigenous scientific and technological capacity in the last decades, becoming the main scientific powerhouse in Asia (Nguyen and Choung, 2020).

The high levels of S&T development reached by countries such as the NICs and BRICS countries in recent decades has led to a decline in the United States, the European Union, and Japan's shares of scientific publications and patents (Veugelers, 2010; Geng and Saggi, 2015; Zhou and Li, 2015). For instance, Zhou and Li (2015:121) point out that the rapid growth of publications by countries such as China, South Korea, and India 'has significantly disturbed the balance of world publication'. Some papers have evidenced this fact, reporting a shift of the world science sources from the West to the East (Radosevic and Yoruk, 2014). Other papers have detailed the same movement to the East in worldwide patenting activity (Barnett, 2020).

Despite the observed change in the geography of scientific and technological production, the empirical evidence about convergence in S&T capabilities across countries is quite scarce and shows mixed results. In addition, most of this research has been conducted by considering a single indicator of a country's S&T capabilities (scientific publications or patents). Some studies have analysed the catch-up process across countries/regions in scientific knowledge production with different results; some of them pointed out the nonexistence of absolute convergence (Asongu and Nwachukwu, 2016), while others found a trend toward convergence (Radosevic and Yoruk, 2014) or the existence of club convergence (Barrios et al., 2021). Similarly, the empirical evidence shows mixed results (convergence and nonconvergence) for patenting activity (Furman et al., 2002; Hu and Matthews, 2005).

This paper adds new evidence to the scarce empirical literature and tries to shed light about whether there is a process of convergence in countries' S&T capabilities. More specifically, we analyse whether the impressive development of S&T systems in emerging knowledge-producing countries in the past decades has led to a convergence with the traditional superpowers in S&T capabilities. The convergence analysis is carried out on a sample of 28 major knowledge-producing countries, including developed Western countries, newly industrialized Asian countries (NICs), and emerging economies such as the BRICS, during the period 2003 to 2016. For the empirical analysis, the S&T capabilities of each country has been operationalised through two indicators related to the outputs of their S&T systems: scientific publications as an indicator of scientific capability, and patents as an indicator of technological capability (Albuquerque, 2001). The methodology used in conducting the empirical convergence analysis first tests whether there has been a total convergence among countries. If this has not occurred, it tests for convergence clubs and divergent behaviours. The existence of convergence has been tested separately for each S&T capability indicator in per capita terms.

The contribution of the paper to the literature on S&T production is threefold. First, it presents an overview of the distribution of scientific publications and patents among the main knowledge-producing countries, and it identifies similarities in S&T specialization profiles. Second, it incorporates new empirical evidence on the process of convergence in S&T capabilities among major knowledge-producing countries in the world using a novel methodology in relation to its application to publications and patents data. Most recent studies focused on knowledge-production convergence analyse it by observing trends in the volume of scientific knowledge or technological knowledge over time. In this paper, the analysis of convergence is directly related to per capita income convergence analysed in economic studies but applied to the S&T arena. In order to do so, the paper uses a methodology that demonstrates whether, in the period analysed, countries in the sample have converged toward the same level of equilibrium of scientific publications per capita and patents per capita, or if they have converged into clubs reaching multiple equilibria. Although the methodology applied is gaining relevance in studies focused on the convergence analysis of socioeconomic variables, its application to S&T data is less well established. Third, the empirical analysis offers valuable information for policy-makers on the convergence process of their country related to other major knowledge-producing countries. This information is especially relevant for lagging countries if they intend to converge with the leaders.

The remainder of this paper falls into five sections. Section 2 briefly reviews the main theoretical perspectives on the role of scientific and technological knowledge in economic growth as well as the empirical literature on convergence in S&T capabilities among countries. Section 3 depicts the data. Section 4 describes the log t test methodology applied in the convergence analysis. Section 5 offers the results of the empirical analysis; some scientific and technological knowledge production characteristics of the countries are described, and then convergence clubs for scientific publications and for patents are identified. Section 6 summarises the main conclusions.

2. Review of the literature

Nations support scientific and technological advances as a source of socioeconomic power, leadership, and reputation in international systems, and as a factor for economic growth and citizens' wellbeing (Coccia, 2019). In modern economies, S&T are essential for knowledge-based economic growth and development (Chandra and Yokoyama, 2011). Factors related to the production, diffusion, acquisition, and use of knowledge have gained importance together with traditional factors of labour and capital for explaining the economic performance of developed and developing countries (Shapira and Youtie, 2006).

Theoretical arguments from diverse economic schools of thought support the key role knowledge plays in long-term economic growth. Neoclassical growth models (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956) consider technological progress as a principal factor explaining long-term economic growth, even if technology is considered to evolve exogenously. Technology is related to information/codified knowledge being easily transferable and accessible to all countries at negligible costs due to its public good features (Laranja et al., 2008). Markets would not be able to provide adequate levels of knowledge production without incentives from the private sector to invest in research and development (R&D), resulting in a market failure needing to be corrected by public policies (Laranja et al., 2008).

The new growth theory developed in the late 1980s also stresses technology as the driving force of endogenous economic growth and development (Fagerberg and Srholec, 2008). Endogenous growth models (Romer, 1986; Lucas, 1988; Romer, 1990) highlight the crucial role played by externalities derived from knowledge accumulation through 'learning by doing' or formation of human capital as well as R&D activity for generating technological progress. In R&D-based endogenous growth models (Romer, 1990; Grossman and Helpman, 1991; Aghion and Howitt, 1992), knowledge generated by the R&D sector is seen as an economic good, and it is considered as a non-rival and partially excludable good (e.g., through IPRs) that responds to market incentives (Castellacci, 2007). According to the knowledge production function used in these models, the rate of knowledge production depends on the amount of labour engaged in R&D and the existing knowledge stock (Abdih and Joutz, 2006). Knowledge is a likely spillover from the public sector to the private sector; within the latter, it is seen as a source of economic growth and leads to increasing returns of scale (Stephan, 1996). R&D-based endogenous models include an active role for public policy in shaping innovation (Furman et al., 2002).

Different modern evolutionary economic theories such as the technology-gap approach (Fagerberg, 1987, 1994; Verspagen, 1991, 1993) and national innovation systems (Freeman, 1987; Lundvall, 2016) also consider technological change as the principal engine of economic growth (Castellacci, 2007). In addition to the innovative capability for producing advanced knowledge, technology-gap models focus on international technology diffusion as a main factor for economic growth and catching up (Castellacci, 2008). The international diffusion of technologies allows technologically backward countries to catch up, acquiring and imitating advanced foreign technologies (Fu et al., 2011). There are diverse mechanisms for international diffusion of technology such as international trade, foreign direct investment (FDI), technology licensing, foreign education of students and workers, international research collaboration, the flow of disembodied knowledge, and integration into a global value chain (Fu et al., 2011; Hu, 2015).

In addition, as Radosevic and Yoruk (2016) note, the modes of technology upgrading are related to income level groups ranging from imitative technology efforts for low-income groups, to technology diversification for middle income (including lower, upper middle and lower high-income) groups, to technology frontier activities for high-income groups. Great attention has been focused on the different catching-up strategies followed by successful Asian countries in developing their technological capabilities and to their economic development and growth (Hu, 2015; Wong and Goh, 2015). For instance, Hu (2015), using the South Korea case, concluded that moving from imitator to innovator is a non-linear process that requires R&D effort and other activities to improve technological capabilities. Wong and Goh (2015) found that the catching-up strategies followed in the process of economic development by South Korea and Taiwan (through mechanisms other than FDI) have led them to higher S&T growth trajectories than those experienced by China and Malaysia, where an FDI-leveraged model for industrialization was implemented; Singapore showed mixed results.

Additionally, as a country increases its economic growth rate, imitating existing advanced technologies, it needs to have a sufficient level of absorptive capacity (Castellacci, 2008). Although in the technology-gap approach absorptive capacity is strongly determined by the level of human capital (Castellacci, 2008), other techno-economic factors and socio-institutional conditions are necessary for successful catching up (Castellacci, 2007).

As Fu et al. (2011) point out, for the international diffusion of technology to be beneficial, it is necessary to complement it with indigenous innovation efforts as well as ‘the presence of modern institutional and governance structures and a conducive innovation system’ (p. 1204). According to Lundvall (2016:86), an innovation system is constituted of ‘elements and relationships that interact in the production, diffusion and use of new and economically useful knowledge’, including a social system that ‘involves interaction between people’ and a dynamic system ‘characterized by both positive feedback and reproduction’. From a broad perspective, a national innovation system (NIS) includes all aspects of the structure of the production system and the institutional setup (Lundvall, 2016). There are differences among countries’ innovation systems in terms of the elements and the relationships among them (Lundvall, 2016); each national innovation system is likely to develop its own unique dynamics (Lundvall, 2007), evolving over time driven by the co-evolution of innovation ability and imitation capacity (Castellacci and Natera, 2013). The NIS approach specifies the active role of government policies and specific institutions in shaping the rate of innovation (Furman et al., 2002).

In the literature on innovation and technological change, the knowledge production function approach formalized by Griliches (1979) has been extensively used in addressing the knowledge-production process linking knowledge output, which is measured by a proxy variable such as patents, with inputs such as R&D expenditure, human capital, skilled labour, and educational levels (Audrestch and Feldman, 2004). Many papers have used a modified knowledge function framework to explain innovative performance at diverse spatial scales such as regions (Marrocu et al., 2013; Charlot et al., 2015; Moreno et al., 2005), including inputs emerging from new economic geography such as agglomeration economies and localised knowledge spillovers, and from an innovation system approach (i.e., region-specific factors) (Ponds et al., 2010). As the literature on R&D spillovers suggests, knowledge spillovers are influenced by geographical and technological proximity (Orlando, 2004) affecting the absorptive capacity of firms (Alder

et al., 2018). As Aldieri et al. (2018) note for the same absorptive capacity, firms located in countries close to the world technology frontier appear to benefit more from pure knowledge spillovers than from rent spillovers that travel along the supply chain, while the opposite occurs for firms located in countries that are not on the technology frontier. Great attention has been paid in this literature to knowledge generated in universities (Acosta et al., 2009; Gurmu et al., 2010; Coronado et al., 2017) and its role as a source of localised knowledge spillover (Del Barrio-Castro and García-Quevedo, 2005; Fritsch and Slavtchev; 2007).

In addition, some empirical papers have focused on convergence in knowledge production among countries. Some of them have considered knowledge production as an indicator of an innovative capability dimension within the NIS framework or from a knowledge-based economy perspective. For instance, Castellacci and Natera (2015) analysed convergence in six dimensions of the NIS of a sample of developed-OECD countries, catching-up countries, and less-developed countries during the period 1980 to 2008. Regarding innovation ability and the technological capability dimension, the authors found a combination of slow β -convergence and σ -divergence for R&D, high-tech products, and scientific publications, and β -divergence and σ -divergence for patents. Asongu and Andrés (2020) analysed convergence in the four knowledge-economy indicators for 21 Middle East and North African (MENA) and sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries from 1996 to 2010. They found that the innovation dimension, measured by scientific and technological journals, shows an absence of absolute convergence, with conditional convergence for both the full sample and MENA, and absolute convergence and conditional convergence for the SSA countries.

Other papers have focused directly on the production of scientific and technological knowledge using diverse estimation methods. For instance, Chen and Chen (2016) used cluster methods to classify 100 countries according to their patterns of scientific publications, grouping them into 12 knowledge-production groups. Asongu and Nwachukwu (2016) analysed convergence in scientific and technical publications from 99 countries around the world following an income convergence methodology, and found the absence of an absolute β -convergence; developed countries continued to dominate scientific production. Barrios et al. (2021) identified five convergence clubs when they analysed the production of scientific publications from 121 developed and developing countries. Veugelers (2010) found evidence of unequal catching-up processes in the production of scientific publications of the non-TRIAD vs. the TRIAD (the US, the EU, and Japan) countries. Confraria et al. (2017) explained the trend toward convergence in scientific knowledge production between countries of the Global North and the Global South on the increase in scientific capacities as well as a presence in high-quality international scientific journals in the latter. Radosevic and Yoruk (2014) found a convergence trend in the production of publications and, to a lesser extent, in impact, within world regions catching up with the world science frontier, suggesting that scientific systems of catching-up economies are improving in relation to the production and impact of scientific knowledge. Furman et al. (2002) analysed innovative capacity (measured by predicted international patents) among 17 OECD countries during the final quarter of the twentieth century, and identified three groups of countries that trend toward convergence. Hu and Matthews (2005) extended the Furman et al. (2002) approach for analysing national innovative capacity to five latecomer East Asian countries (Taiwan, South Korea, Singapore, Hong Kong, and China), finding divergence in patenting activity among them. Geng and Saggi (2015) found that China presents a very different evolutionary pattern in terms of patent

applications filed during the period 1997 to 2011 from the other countries in the BRICS group (Brazil, India, and Russia).

3. Data

In the paper, data on scientific publications produced by each country from 2003 to 2016 come from the ‘S&E articles indicator’ of the US National Science Foundation dataset (NSF, 2016), and it refers to publication counts in S&E from Scopus. The NSF (2016) dataset offers the total number of publications produced for each country each year as well as distribution in the following fields of science: Agricultural Sciences, Astronomy, Biological Sciences, Chemistry, Computer Sciences, Engineering, Geosciences, Mathematics, Medical Sciences, Other Life Sciences, Physics, Psychology, and Social Sciences.

Patent data also came from the National Science Foundation dataset (NSF, 2016) and refer to patents granted by the US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO). As some studies point out, differences in national patent regulations make international patenting activity comparison difficult, which is why it is usually analysed in a foreign market such as the US market (Fagerberg, 1987; Wong and Goh, 2013; Su, 2017). In the NSF (2016) dataset, patents are classified into 20 technological fields grouped into four categories: ‘ITC’ (Basic communication process, Computer, Digital communications, IT management, Semiconductors, Telecommunications); ‘Testing, measuring, and control’ (Analysis of biological materials, Control, Measurement, and Optics); ‘Chemistry and health’ (Pharmaceuticals, Biotechnology, Basic material chemistry, Organic chemistry, Macromolecular chemistry, Chemical engineering, and Medical technology); and ‘Materials and nanotechnology’ (Materials and metallurgy, Microstructural and nanotechnology, and Surface technology and coating).

Both publications and patents are credited on a fractional-count basis. For our convergence analysis, scientific publications and patents have been considered in per capita terms normalized by population extracted from World Bank data.

The sample contains 28 developed and emerging economies including Western countries, NICs countries, and BRICS countries: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, China, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, India, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Malaysia, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Russia, Singapore, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The sample accounted for nearly 90% of the world's scientific publications and around 98% of the world's patents in the analyzed period (see Table 1). In addition, the choice of countries has been conditioned by the availability of data for both S&T capabilities indicators in the NSF (2016) dataset.

4. Methodology

The concept of convergence used in the paper comes from the literature on convergence analysis regarding economic variables. Applied to the S&T field, the absolute β convergence hypothesis establishes that all countries will converge toward the same long-run steady state of scientific publications (or patents) per capita, while the convergence club hypothesis implies that countries with similar initial and structural conditions regarding the production of scientific publications (or patents) per capita will tend to converge

together to the same steady state; thus, different groups of countries (clubs) would exhibit multiple steady state equilibria.

The convergence analysis is conducted by applying the Phillips and Sul (PS) convergence test (2007, 2009). The PS log t test is a nonlinear factor model that uses stationary or non-stationary data while capturing absolute and club convergence as well as transitional heterogeneity. It is also able to overcome the omitted variable bias and it is useful in examining transitional behavior. The test is a regression that can also provide groupings that do not depend on eventual assumptions about the stationary trend of the examined variables (Monfort et al., 2013).

The variables of interest are scientific publications and patents per capita for all countries, which is denoted as X_{it} where $i = \{1, \dots, N\}$ and $t = \{1, \dots, T\}$ with N referring to the total number of countries (28), and t ranging from 2003 to 2016. Hence, the PS model (2007, 2009) introduces a cross-sectional analysis as well as a heterogeneous time series analysis in the parameters of a neoclassical growth model in order to form the data panel $\{X_{it}\}$.

The natural log of X_{it} , which is $\text{Ln}(X_{it})$, is used and is broken into two components:

$$\text{Ln}(X_{it}) \approx \varphi_i \mu_t, \quad (1)$$

where φ_i is the component containing the idiosyncratic factors of each country while μ_t represents the common stochastic trends.

To take into account the heterogeneity of a temporary transition variable, h_{it} (equation 2), is analyzed. In this formulation, the factor-loading portion, φ_i , measures the distance between X_{it} and common factor μ_t .

Given the data panel $\{X_{it}\}$, the following steps are performed. First, for each time t , the mean value is calculated, and each individual value, X_{it} , is compared against the obtained average value of:

$$h_{it} = \frac{X_{it}}{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N X_{it}}{N}} \quad (2)$$

A panel of $\{h_{it}\}$ is formed from h_{it} for all 28 countries and years from 2003 to 2016 from equation (2) with the elimination of the initial X_{it} .

The second step involves the variance of the h_{it} values for each time t , with the variance being calculated from the following formula:

$$H_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (h_{it} - 1)^2}{N} \quad (3)$$

The reason for comparing each h_{it} value to 1 is that if there is convergence, all these values should converge to 1, which are the transition curves.

In order to specify the null hypothesis of convergence, PS (2007) formulate the idiosyncratic element φ_{it} as:

$$\varphi_{it} = \varphi_i + \frac{\sigma_i \varepsilon_{it}}{L(t)^\alpha} \quad (4)$$

where φ_i is fixed, σ_i is an idiosyncratic scale parameter, ε_{it} is iid(0,1) across i , $L(t)$ is a slowly varying function such as $\text{Ln}(t)$ ($L(t) \rightarrow \infty$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$), and α denotes the speed of convergence.

The null hypothesis of convergence is formulated as:

$$H_0: \varphi_i = \varphi \text{ and } \alpha \geq 0$$

against the alternative of no convergence, which is

$$H_A: \varphi_i \neq \varphi \text{ for all } i \text{ or } \alpha < 0.$$

The absolute convergence hypothesis is based on the fact that H_t tends to zero. To test for absolute convergence, the following model is used:

$$\ln H_t = a + \beta \ln(t) + u_t, \text{ where } t = [rT], [rT] + 1, \dots, T. \quad (5)$$

Based on Monte Carlo simulations provided by PS (2007), it is suggested that $r = 0.30$ for sample sizes below $T = 50$. If $\beta < 0$, then the absolute convergence hypothesis, i.e., σ -convergence, is rejected and the next step is to proceed to testing for conditional convergence, specifically club convergence, using the value obtained for β .

To test for club convergence, i.e., β -convergence, an iterative algorithm developed by PS (2007) is applied and tested at the 95% significance level, which they refer to as the log t test. The iterative procedure to identify convergence clubs is summarized in four steps:

The panel data are ordered from the highest to lowest based on the observations of the last period.

The next step is to select k in the panel countries to form each club, where k is the number of members of each club. This begins to form groups of countries, i.e., clubs, from the highest value of each variable in the last period, so that the clubs could contain anywhere from $2 \leq k < N$ members, where the size of the club is determined based on the estimated t-statistic of the estimated coefficient of $\ln(t)$, which is β from equation (5). As long as the estimated t-statistic is > -1.65 , the country is counted as being in the club.

If, in the previous step, two countries meet the established criterion, the process will continue to add countries in the order in which they appear in the data panel, which is already sorted. As long as the data continue to meet the criterion, the country is added to the club. When the data no longer meet the criterion, the first club is formed and completed.

The fourth and final step for the remaining countries is to iteratively apply steps (1) to (3) in order to find successive clubs. The countries show divergent behaviour if no core group can be found.

Phillips and Sul (2007) also propose modelling the transitional elements φ_{it} by building a relative measure based on the average value provided in Equation (2):

$$h_{it} = \frac{X_{it}}{\sum_{i=1}^N X_{it}} = \frac{\varphi_{it}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \varphi_{it}} \quad (6)$$

This measures the weighted coefficients, φ_{it} , in relation to the panel data. The variable h_{it} is called the relative transition path. It traces an individual path for each country i relative to the average of the panel data. Thus, h_{it} measures the trajectory of each country i from the starting position relative to the path of common growth. When there is common behaviour in the path of growth between countries, $h_{it} = h_t$, a convergence club between that group is formed and, in the same way, a path of common growth for the club in the panel data can be traced.

Studying convergence in a panel data set has several appealing features. Since the model traces an individual path for each country i relative to the average panel data, we can distinguish, empirically, different degrees of convergence. The regression coefficient β provides a scaled estimator of the speed of convergence, parameter α ; specifically, $\beta = 2\alpha$.

5. Results

This section is organized in two parts. Firstly, it provides an overview of distribution of scientific publications and patents production across the selected countries, as well as of their similarities in scientific and technological knowledge production. Secondly, it presents the results of convergence analysis in their S&T capabilities.

5.1 Descriptive analysis

Table 1 provides the number of scientific publications by country in 2003 and 2016, and for the entire period 2003-2016. Countries are ranked in descending order by the total number of scientific publications in the period 2003-2016. The United States and China appear as the major scientific powers, followed by Japan, Germany, and the United Kingdom. These top five countries accounted for 52.03% of the world's scientific publications in the period 2003-2016.

It is remarkable that the United States, which has traditionally occupied the top rank as the leading producer of scientific publications, was surpassed by China in 2016. The loss in the United States' contribution to the world total is of 9.16 percentage points (from 26.98% in 2003 to 17.82% in 2016), while China increased 11.30 percentage points (from 7.26% in 2003 to 18.56% in 2016). In the period 2003-2016, China produced 14.91% of the world total versus 21.42% generated by the United States.

The number of total world scientific publications has risen nearly twofold between 2003 and 2016. All countries have shown an upward trend except Japan, which has slightly reduced its scientific production (by 0.72%). The rapid growth in the number of scientific publications between 2003 and 2016 in new knowledge-producing countries such as Malaysia (up elevenfold since 2003), China (up fivefold), India (up fourfold), Brazil (up threefold), South Africa and South Korea (each nearly up threefold) is notable, while most established scientific powers have experienced more moderate increases.

Table 1. Number of scientific publications by country.

Country	Number of scientific publications 2003	% (1)	2003 Rank	Number of scientific publications 2016	% (2)	2016 Rank	Total scientific publications 2003-2016	%	Change 2003-2016 ^a (%)
United States	321,765.90	26.98	1	408,985.30	17.82	2	5,593,381.10	21.42	27.11
China	86,621.40	7.26	3	426,165.30	18.56	1	3,894,298.10	14.91	391.99
Japan	97,235.20	8.15	2	96,536.20	4.21	6	1,481,747.60	5.67	-0.72
Germany	70,447.70	5.91	5	103,121.90	4.49	4	1,313,562.10	5.03	46.38
United Kingdom	74,599.80	6.26	4	97,526.90	4.25	5	1,304,369.50	5.00	30.73
France	51,757.80	4.34	6	69,430.80	3.02	7	938,194.70	3.59	34.15

India	26,797.10	2.25	11	110,319.60	4.81	3	901,429.40	3.45	311.68
Italy	41,207.10	3.46	7	69,125.20	3.01	8	814,949.60	3.12	67.75
Canada	37,695.50	3.16	8	57,355.80	2.50	11	751,743.30	2.88	52.16
South Korea	23,201.10	1.95	13	63,063.00	2.75	9	663,345.30	2.54	171.81
Spain	28,887.20	2.42	10	52,820.70	2.30	13	645,537.10	2.47	82.85
Australia	24,849.70	2.08	12	51,068.20	2.22	14	565,656.90	2.17	105.51
Brazil	16,752.40	1.40	15	53,606.60	2.34	12	538,730.80	2.06	219.99
Russia	32,329.50	2.71	9	59,133.50	2.58	10	525,008.60	2.01	82.91
Taiwan	15,807.30	1.33	16	27,385.10	1.19	16	398,004.90	1.52	73.24
Netherlands	19,565.00	1.64	14	29,949.00	1.30	15	386,316.50	1.48	53.07
Switzerland	12,848.20	1.08	18	21,127.60	0.92	17	258,535.70	0.99	64.44
Sweden	14,553.80	1.22	17	19,937.10	0.87	19	250,984.90	0.96	36.99
Belgium	10,811.80	0.91	19	16,393.70	0.71	20	208,045.50	0.80	51.63
Austria	7,749.60	0.65	21	12,366.40	0.54	22	151,191.40	0.58	59.57
Denmark	7,279.60	0.61	22	13,470.70	0.59	21	149,289.40	0.57	85.05
Malaysia	1,741.10	0.15	28	20,331.50	0.89	18	140,333.00	0.54	1,067.74
Finland	7,792.30	0.65	20	10,545.10	0.46	26	137,601.40	0.53	35.33
Singapore	6,037.00	0.51	23	11,253.80	0.49	24	130,822.90	0.50	86.41
Norway	5,118.60	0.43	24	10,725.70	0.47	25	120,276.00	0.46	109.54
South Africa	4,226.60	0.35	26	11,881.20	0.52	23	110,260.10	0.42	181.11
New Zealand	4,395.80	0.37	25	7,464.70	0.33	27	91,236.60	0.35	69.81
Ireland	3,069.30	0.26	27	6,834.40	0.30	28	84,213.70	0.32	122.67
Word	1,192,446			2,295,608			26,112,073	100	92.5
Accumulated % over total World		88.49			84.42			86.35	
C5*		54.57			49.33			52.03	

^a Change 2003-2016 is the percentage change in the number of scientific publications between 2003 and 2016.

C5*: This is the accumulated percentage over total word for the top 5 countries.

Table 2 displays data on the number of patents by country in 2003 and 2016 and the total value for the period 2003-2016. Countries are ranked in descending order by the total number of patents in the period 2003-2016. The United States stands out as the world superpower with the highest number of granted patents (around 50% of world patents in the period 2003-2016), followed by Japan (with 19.65% of world patents); Germany, South Korea, and Taiwan also figure in the top 5, but with a certain distance from the leading countries (the United States and Japan). The top five countries with the largest number of patents accounted for 82.78% of the world's patents in the period 2003-2016. Advanced technological powers remained at high levels but displayed moderate growth in comparison with the rapid increase of some emerging Asian countries such as China (with an increase above 1,700% between 2003-2016) and India (with a growth above 900%). The case of China is especially remarkable; its contribution to the world's patent production has risen from 0.37% in 2003 to 3.76% in 2016, surpassing in 2016 the number of patents in other technologically established countries such as Sweden, France, Canada, and the United Kingdom.

Finally, when the countries' share of world patents (columns (1) and (2) in Table 2) and the countries' share of world publications (columns (1) and (2) in Table 1) are compared, it can be observed

that most of the countries are more intensive in the production of scientific knowledge than in technological innovations; that is, they have a higher share of world publications than world patents. Only four countries present the opposite pattern, showing a greater contribution to the world production of technological knowledge than to global scientific production. The countries are Japan, Taiwan, the United States, and South Korea. However, in general, there is a trend in all countries toward an increase in their technological intensity during the analyzed period.

Table 2. Number of patents by country.

Country	Number of patents 2003	% (1)	2003 Rank	Number of patents 2016	% (2)	2016 Rank	Total patents 2003-2016	%	Change 2003-2016* (%)
United States	87,579	51.80	1	143,190	47.08	1	1,470,225	48.75	63.50
Japan	35,567	21.04	2	50,169	16.50	2	592,674	19.65	41.05
Germany	11,462	6.78	3	15,975	5.25	4	171,265	5.68	39.37
South Korea	3,952	2.34	5	19,576	6.44	3	147,044	4.88	395.34
Taiwan	5,299	3.13	4	11,576	3.81	5	115,174	3.82	118.46
Canada	3,448	2.04	8	6,503	2.14	8	66,206	2.20	88.60
France	3,879	2.29	6	6,465	2.13	9	63,509	2.11	66.67
United Kingdom	3,661	2.17	7	6,603	2.17	7	63,339	2.10	80.36
China	622	0.37	16	11,449	3.76	6	55,691	1.85	1740.68
Italy	1,723	1.02	9	2,712	0.89	12	26,713	0.89	57.40
Sweden	1,511	0.89	10	2,863	0.94	11	24,159	0.80	89.48
Netherlands	1,330	0.79	12	2,600	0.85	14	24,085	0.80	95.49
Switzerland	1,335	0.79	11	2,631	0.87	13	23,300	0.77	97.08
India	354	0.21	20	3,767	1.24	10	20,490	0.68	964.12
Australia	909	0.54	13	1,561	0.51	15	19,794	0.66	71.73
Finland	868	0.51	14	1,513	0.50	16	14,668	0.49	74.31
Belgium	636	0.38	15	1,238	0.41	18	11,248	0.37	94.65
Austria	595	0.35	17	1,367	0.45	17	10,720	0.36	129.75
Denmark	537	0.32	18	1,084	0.36	19	9,250	0.31	101.86
Singapore	438	0.26	19	989	0.33	20	8,627	0.29	125.80
Spain	325	0.19	21	795	0.26	21	6,909	0.23	144.62
Norway	258	0.15	22	609	0.20	22	5,196	0.17	136.05
Russia	223	0.13	23	557	0.18	24	4,362	0.14	149.78
Ireland	163	0.10	24	590	0.19	23	4,205	0.14	261.96
Brazil	132	0.08	25	318	0.10	25	2,619	0.09	140.91
New Zealand	137	0.08	25	270	0.09	27	2,503	0.08	97.08
Malaysia	48	0.03	27	275	0.09	26	2,458	0.08	472.92
South Africa	111	0.07	26	181	0.06	27	1,709	0.06	63.06
Word	169,077			304,126			3,015,767		79.87
Accumulated % over total World		98.83			97.80			98.42	
C5*		85.08			79.07			82.78	

* Change 2003-2016 is the perceptual change in the number of patents between 2003 and 2016.

C5*: This is the accumulated percentage over total word for the top 5 countries.

Based on national publications and patents data, we identify similarities in scientific and technological specialization among countries. Firstly, we have calculated scientific and technological specialization indexes, and then we have separately grouped countries with similar specializations in scientific publications and in patents. The revealed scientific advantage index (RSA) (Fung and Wong, 2017) is used for measuring scientific specialization, and the revealed technological advantage index (RTA) (Cantwell, 1989) for technological specialization¹.

The index of scientific (technological) specialization is calculated as:

$$RSA(RTA) = (P_{ij}/\sum P_j) / (\sum P_{iw}/\sum P_w)$$

where P_{ij} is the number of publications in scientific field i (the number of patents in technological area i) of country j ; P_j is the number of publications (the number of patents) in country j ; P_{iw} is the number of publications in scientific field i (the number of patents in technological area i) across the world; and P_w is the total number of publications in all scientific fields (the number of patents in all technological areas) across the world.

Based on the RSA indexes for the period 2003-2016, Ward's method of hierarchical grouping has been applied to identify groups of countries that present a similar scientific specialization in the 13 scientific fields described in Section 3 (Figure 1). It has proceeded in a similar way, but using the RTA indexes to detect groups of countries whose patenting activity is similar considering the four technology categories described in Section 3 (Figure 2).

¹ Values of RSA (RTA) greater (or lesser) than 1 mean that the country has a comparative advantage (disadvantage) in that scientific (technological) field relative to the world average.

Figure 1. Cluster analysis with the RSA index. Figure 2. Cluster analysis with the RTA index.

Regarding RSA values, as Figure 1 shows, the countries can be clustered into two large groups. Group 1 includes Australia, the United Kingdom, Canada, the United States, Sweden, the Netherlands, Norway, Ireland, New Zealand, South Africa, and Brazil (which joined the group at a much later stage). When comparing disciplinary specialization among clusters, it can be observed that group 1 has the highest values of all clusters for applied scientific fields related to life sciences such as Agricultural Sciences (highlighting the high RSA of New Zealand, Ireland, and Brazil); Biological Sciences (most countries are above average); and Other Life Sciences (all countries are above average except Australia and Ireland). Group 1 also has the highest values for Medical Sciences (most countries are above average); Geosciences (highlighting Norway); and Psychology and Social Sciences (the majority of countries are above average, with the Netherlands and New Zealand notable in the first field, and South Africa and the United Kingdom in the second). In addition, group 1 presents the lowest values for two basic scientific fields, Chemistry and Physics, and two applied fields, Computer Sciences and Engineering, in which all countries are below average (except for Ireland in Computer Sciences). For Astronomy and Mathematics, group 1 has RSA values between groups 2.1 and 2.2, being below the average in both fields.

The countries of group 2 can also be divided into two groups. Germany, Switzerland, Austria, France, Italy, Belgium, Spain, Finland, Denmark, and Russia (which joined the group at a much later stage) belong to group 2.1. This group has the highest values for two basic fields, Astronomy and Mathematics, in which the majority of counties are above average (Russia stands out in both fields, and Italy in the first); the lowest value for Agricultural Sciences (all countries are below the average except Spain and Denmark); and are quite similar to group 1 for Medical Sciences. The rest of the scientific fields have values between groups 2.1 and 2.2. Group 2.2, formed by all Asian countries of the sample—China, India, Japan, Malaysia, Singapore, South Korea, and Taiwan—presents the highest values for two basic fields, Chemistry and

Physics (all countries are above the average, except India and Malaysia for Physics), and two applied fields, Computer Sciences and Engineering (all countries are above the average except Japan for Computer Sciences). This group has the lowest values for Psychology, Social Sciences, Astronomy, Geosciences, Biological Sciences, Other Life Sciences, and Medical Sciences.

In relation to RTA values, as Figure 2 displays, countries can also be clustered into two groups. Over all, group 1 presents the highest values for ‘Chemistry and health’, ‘Materials and nanotechnology’ and ‘Testing, measuring and control’ technologies. In turn, group 1 can be divided into three groups. Group 1.1 is composed of Australia, Germany, France, Austria, Russia, the Netherlands, Norway, and Switzerland; it presents the highest value for ‘Testing, measuring and control’ technology. Within this technology, all or almost all countries are above average in Measurement and Analysis; all countries are below the average for Optics (except Russia), and half of them are above the average in Control, highlighting Australia. Group 1.2, formed by Italy, Spain, Denmark, and New Zealand, has neither the highest nor the lowest values for any of the technologies, but it has values above the average for ‘Chemistry and health’ and ‘Materials and nanotechnology’, and below the average for ‘ICT’ and ‘Testing, measuring, and control’. Belgium, Brazil, and South Africa belong to group 1.3. This group presents the highest values for ‘Chemistry and health’ and ‘Materials and nanotechnology’, with all countries above the average in both fields. It has the lowest values for ‘ICT’ and ‘Testing, measuring, and control’, with all countries below the average in both fields.

Group 2 can be divided into two groups. Countries of group 2.1 (Canada, Sweden, Ireland, the United Kingdom, and India) have neither the highest nor the lowest values for any of the technologies. All countries are above the average in ‘ICT’; most are above the average in ‘Chemistry and health’ and below in ‘Materials and nanotechnology’. The countries of group 2.2 (Finland, Singapore, China, Malaysia, South Korea, Taiwan, the United States, and Japan) have the highest value for ‘ICT’. Within ‘ICT’ technology, all countries (except Finland, Japan, and Singapore) are above the average in Computer; Singapore, Malaysia, Taiwan, and South Korea stand out in Semiconductors, with Finland and the US below the average. In Telecommunications and Digital technologies, Finland stands out, Singapore and Malaysia are below the average in both, while Japan and Taiwan are below the average in the latter. In Basic communication processes, Malaysia, Singapore, South Korea, and Taiwan are above the average; and in IT management, only Finland and the United States are above the average. Group 2.2 presents the lowest values for ‘Chemistry and health’ and ‘Materials and nanotechnology’.

At first glance, the comparison of the members of the clusters in publications and patents suggests that, among the S&T traditional superpowers, there is no clear common specialization profile. Rather, differences in scientific and technological specialization profiles emerge among these countries. Within the BRICS, Brazil and South Africa seem to have S&T profiles somewhat more similar to the rest of the BRICS countries. Russia presents a profile more similar to some European countries than to the other BRICS in both indicators. India shows a specialization more similar to the rest of the Asian countries in publications, while in technology its specialization is more similar to that of certain Western countries. The rest of the Asian countries (China, South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, Japan, and Malaysia) are grouped together, with similar profiles for scientific publications and patents.

5.2. Convergence in S&T capabilities: Scientific publications and patents per capita

In this section, we examine the patterns of convergence in S&T knowledge production for the set of 28 countries from 2003 to 2016. First, we study the patterns of convergence in scientific publications per capita and second, in patents per capita.

Table 3 displays the results of applying the PS log t test to scientific publications per capita. The results indicate that the hypothesis of overall convergence is strongly rejected at the 5% significance level since the value of the estimated t-statistic (-41.2791) is less than the critical value of -1.65. The next step is to check for the existence of convergence clubs by applying the PS (2007) algorithm. As seen in results of the previous process, four clubs and two divergent countries (the United Kingdom and France) are found. Figure 3 depicts the transition paths of the identified clubs and the divergent countries.

Clubs 1 and 2 are made up of half of the European countries in the sample—all the Nordic countries, Switzerland, and the Netherlands—plus Australia and Singapore. They have the highest ratio of scientific publications per capita (2.3281 per 1,000 inhabitants and 1.9485 per 1,000 inhabitants, respectively, for 2016) (Table 3). Club 1 is the most cohesive, with a speed of convergence of 0.4255; conversely, Club 2 is the weakest, with values of t-statistic that reach a negative value of -1.3019 but still are greater than -1.65. These clubs have transition paths (Figure 3) that smoothly go down from 2003 to 2016, separating slightly at the end of the period. Club 3 is the most numerous (12 countries) and is formed of the rest of the European countries, the United States, Canada, New Zealand, South Korea, Taiwan, and Malaysia. This is a cohesive club, but the speed of convergence is not as high, with a value of 0.0446. Club 3 has a medium ratio of scientific publications per capita, as is shown in its transition path in Figure 3. Overall, the transition paths of these three clubs seem to show a trend toward convergence, decreasing the distances between them at the end of the period. Club 4 is the most laggard club; it is formed of the BRICS countries and Japan. Its transition path is clearly below unity (Figure 3), although with an upward trend in the analyzed period, showing the efforts of these countries to increase the number of scientific publications per capita. In addition, the United Kingdom and France show divergent behavior. The transition paths also show a decreasing trend toward unity, although in the case of France, after 2007, it has performed below Club 3.

Table 3: Convergence club classification scientific publications per capita.

PANEL A (Scientific publications per 1,000 inhabitants): Log t regression results						
Club	Log t regression			Descriptive statistics		
	Number of countries	Beta	t-statistic*	Scientific publications per 1,000 inhabitants 2003	Scientific publications per 1,000 inhabitants 2016	Average annual growth rate 2003-2016
All countries	28	-0.8385	-41.2791			
Club 1	3	0.4255	2.2468	1.5555	2.3281	3.82%
Club 2	5	-0.8508	-1.3019	1.3827	1.9485	3.15%

Club 3	12	0.0446	0.5156	0.8055	1.2787	4.52%
Club 4	6	0.0139	0.1153	0.2095	0.3388	4.75%

PANEL A: Club membership

Club 1	Switzerland, Denmark, Australia
Club 2	Norway, Sweden, Singapore, Finland, Netherlands
Club 3	New Zealand, Canada, Belgium, Ireland, Austria, South Korea, Malaysia, the United States, Germany, Taiwan, Italy, Spain
Club 4	Japan, Russia, China, Brazil, South Africa, India
Divergent	The United Kingdom, France

*The log t test is distributed as a one-sided t-statistic with a 5% critical value of -1.65.

Figure 3: Transition paths of convergence clubs for scientific publications per capita.

In the same way, when the iterative log t test is applied to per capita patents across all 28 countries (Table 4), the hypothesis of overall convergence is strongly rejected at the 5% significance level since the value of the estimated t-statistic is -6.4741, which does not reach the critical value of -1.65. As there is no absolute convergence, we proceed to check for clustering using the PS (2007) club convergence model. The results show the existence of six clubs and two divergent countries (Taiwan and Italy), as shown in Table 4. Figure 4 displays the transition paths for the six convergence clubs and the two divergent countries.

Table 4: Convergence club classification patents per capita.

PANEL B (Patents per 1,000 inhabitants): Log t regression results

Club	Log t regression			Descriptive statistics		
	Number of countries	Beta	t-statistic*	Patents per million inhabitants 2003	Patents per million inhabitants 2016	Average annual growth rate 2003-2016
All countries	28	-0.8695	-6.4741			
Club 1	7	-0.2477	-1.4772	186.5	279.4	3.83%

Club 2	6	-0.0601	-0.2129	75.4	149.1	7.51%
Club 3	4	0.7439	1.1429	61.1	92.7	3.97%
Club 4	2	-0.4493	-0.4075	31.4	61.1	7.29%
Club 5	2	-0.1416	-1.0662	4.2	11.5	13.6%
Club 6	5	0.0642	0.3302	0.9	3.5	21.1%

PANEL B: Club membership

Club 1	United States, Japan, South Korea, Switzerland, Sweden, Canada, Denmark
Club 2	Finland, Germany, Singapore, Netherlands, Austria, Ireland
Club 3	Belgium, France, Norway, United Kingdom
Club 4	Australia, New Zealand
Club 5	Spain, Malaysia
Club 6	China, Russia, South Africa, India, Brazil
Divergent	Taiwan, Italy

*The log t test is distributed as a one-sided t-statistic with a 5% critical value of -1.65.

Figure 4: Transition paths of convergence clubs for patents per capita.

Japan and South Korea, together with the United States, Canada, Sweden, Denmark, and Switzerland belong to the club with the highest level of patents per capita (Club 1), well above the rest. Clubs 2 and 3 are formed by the rest of the European countries (except Spain) and Singapore. The transition paths of these three clubs are above unity and go down a little from 2003 to 2016. Within these three clubs, Club 3 is the most cohesive, with a speed of convergence of 0.7439. Conversely, Club 4 is a weak convergence club (t-statistic = -0.4075); it is formed by Australia and New Zealand; and its relative transition path is around unity (Fig. 4). Club 5 is formed by Spain and Malaysia, while the BRICS countries form Club 6. These last two clubs, which lag the farthest behind, have experienced the highest annual growth rates for patents, 13.6% and 21.1%, respectively (Table 4). The transition paths of Club 5 and Club 6 are clearly below unity, but with a sustained and very pronounced growth over the period. Finally,

Taiwan, although divergent, shows more advanced behavior in terms of patents per capita production than Club 1; in fact, its transition path is above all clubs. In contrast, Italy shows a decreasing transition path, placing it below unity at the end of the period.

6. Conclusions

The role of knowledge in current societies is well known to be a crucial factor for economic growth. As Lundvall (2016) states, in the modern economy knowledge is the more important resource and learning is the most important process. During the past few decades, many countries on all continents have launched policy initiatives to become knowledge-based economies as they seek to encourage economic development and growth (Hollanders and Soete, 2011). As a result, the global production of scientific and technological knowledge has been raised due not only to the contributions of traditional advanced scientific and technological powers, but also to the pronounced growth in S&T knowledge production of emerging countries. This has caused the world share in the production of scientific and technological knowledge in the advanced powers to decrease while it has increased for the emerging nations.

The paper investigates whether globalization in the production of S&T has led to a process of convergence in the levels of scientific publications and patents per capita among the major knowledge-producing countries worldwide. The empirical research was comprised of two parts. Firstly, a descriptive analysis was conducted with a twofold objective: to examine the distribution of scientific publications and patents among the countries of the sample, and to shed light on the similarities in scientific and technological specialization among them. Secondly, log t test methodology was applied to per capita scientific publications and per capita patents to examine whether leading knowledge-producing countries are converging in S&T capabilities.

The results of the descriptive analysis suggest, on the one hand, a high concentration in the patents granted and, to a lesser extent, in the production of scientific publications, as well as a global change in the geography of S&T production activity, with increasing weight in the emerging countries. Although countries exhibit different scientific and technological specialization profiles, groups of countries with similar scientific publications and patent production characteristics have been identified.

Regarding convergence analysis based on log t test methodology, we found that there has not been an absolute convergence in scientific publications per capita or in patents per capita. Instead, we find convergence within several clubs; that is, we identified convergence clubs in S&T capabilities, although with differences in the number of clubs and their composition.

Four groups of countries (and two divergent countries, France and the United Kingdom) have been shown to converge regarding their scientific publications per capita, and six convergence clubs (and two divergent countries, Italy and Taiwan) have been detected when patents per capita are considered. Some common patterns with respect to the composition of both scientific and technological clubs can be observed. First, all Western traditional superpowers and NICs countries are in scientific and technological convergence clubs situated above or at the panel average (see Fig 1 and Fig 2). Second, the BRICS economies belong to the science and technology clubs that lag the most. In spite of the aforementioned, some differences emerge in the composition of clubs. Thus, there are countries that perform better in

technology than in science (Austria, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, and the United States). Others show the opposite pattern; they are in clubs that are more advanced in science than in technology (Australia, Malaysia, Norway, and Spain); and there is a group of countries that lead in both scientific and technological clubs (Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands, Singapore, Sweden, and Switzerland).

These results are consistent with what previous literature has shown. NICs countries such as South Korea and Taiwan have favored the building of their technological capabilities, passing from imitators (through absorption, improvement, and assimilation of foreign technologies) to innovators (Wong and Goh, 2015). Further, this process has been accompanied by the adoption of a science policy that has led to further development of applied sciences necessary for the industrial sector (Kim and Lee, 2015). In the case of Singapore, public support from local government and the application of a model 'brain-gain game' to attract the best foreign talent to local universities have been key to converting the country into a main science and technology hub (McGilvray, 2016).

Some Latin American countries such as Brazil have initially imported foreign technologies, but have not been able to develop local technological capabilities, and their science sectors have focused mainly on basic research that was less relevant to the industrial sector (Kim and Lee, 2015).

With respect to the results of other emerging countries in the production of S&T knowledge in our sample, although China and India have notably increased the production of scientific publications and patents in absolute terms, when their dynamics of growth in S&T outcomes are considered in per capita terms (club convergence analysis), they have not reached the levels of other advanced countries. In club convergence classification, Malaysia remains in a relatively lagging positions in the S&T top league because it began at low values despite the growth experienced during the analysed period. As Govindaraju and Wong (2011) have pointed out, the local native innovative capabilities of Malaysia are still weak and dependent on the level of inward FDI. Similarly, the efforts to develop basic research have yet to generate the kind of local growth in scientific output manifested in South Korea and Taiwan (Wong and Goh, 2015).

The implications of our results are as follows. First, the observed convergence in the S&T capabilities among the major knowledge-producing countries indicates that countries cluster around different long-run equilibria rather than at a single steady-state equilibrium in terms of publications per capita and of patents per capita. Second, the analysis carried out allows knowing with whom each country converges, the transitional behaviour of the clubs, and the situation of each country related to the other countries/clubs. This provides insights for policy-makers as they evaluate the effectiveness of different S&T policies and can help them identify the countries that have been most successful in their strategies to arrive at or get closer to the world S&T frontier.

Finally, it would be interesting to know what factors may explain the formation of scientific publications and patents clubs, and the role they play in both cases. This issue is beyond the scope of this paper, and should be addressed in future research. The recognition of these factors may guide policymakers in implementing S&T policies that boost the production of scientific and technological knowledge. This information is especially important for lagging countries if they wish to catch up with the leaders.

7. References

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